

DAMAGE CHARACTERIZATION ON STIFFNESS LOSS OF MULTI-DIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH MATRIX CRACKS

A. Asundi¹, Y.J. Liu¹, S. Y. Du² and C. L. Chow³

Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Hong Kong, HK¹

School of Astronautics, Harbin Institute of Technology, China²

Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Michigan-Dearborn³
Dearborn, MI 48128-1491, USA

ABSTRACT

An investigation of damaged multi-directional laminates has been made based on the concept of damage mechanics(DM) containing matrix cracks in off-axis plies. The dissipative damage process due to matrix cracking is approximated by a sequence of constrained equilibrium states corresponding to the instantaneous arrangements of micro-structures. Hence, a constitutive framework is constructed based on an incremental form of the damage mechanism theory, in that mechanical property degradation caused due to damage can be described by a damage strain. The validity of proposed model is checked by comparing with those predicted and measured experimentally for various multi-directional laminates.

Keywords: damage, laminates, matrix cracking

1. INTRODUCTION

Experimental evidence has revealed that matrix cracking in off-axis plies is initiated when the applied load increases beyond a threshold value. It will grow parallel to fiber direction within each individual layer without intruding into the lateral laminae due to the constrain of adjacent plies and tend to become saturated prior to the onset of delamination. These complex damage processes occurring in high-performance composite laminates cause material property degradation, such as the loss of stiffness[1] and thus significantly reduce the final load-bearing capability of the laminates. Extensive effort has been devoted in the characterization of this damage phenomenon both at macroscopic level, e.g. damage mechanics, and microscopic level by summarizing numerous microdefects to grossly simplified mathematical models. However, both approaches have weaknesses and limitations, especially in the determination of shear modulus. Consequently, the development of a rigorous constitutive model in the damage assessment of composite laminates is called for. An effort made in this paper is intended to extend the recently developed theory of DM by the authors[2] to include the constitutive analysis of laminated materials containing matrix cracks. The damage is considered as a continuous and homogeneous "physical field" in each individual ply and the relating damage variable is formulated by a second-order tensor directly deduced from the microscopic discontinuous variables, representing displacements due to matrix cracking. The predicted loss of stiffness for various stacking sequences of laminates by the proposed model are in agreement with the experimental results.

2. THERMODYNAMIC CONSTITUTIVE FRAMEWORK AND DAMAGE VARIABLE

2.1. Representation of damage

From the basic assumption of DM, matrix cracking, as a damage process, may be considered as a thermodynamic irreversible processes. Hence, it can be described by a sequence of constrained equilibrium states corresponding to the instantaneous values of internal variables (damage variable). Since a cloud of matrix cracks may occur in off-axis ply, which predominantly cause reduction in laminates stiffness, we may postulate that:

Damaged laminates degradation, i.e. stiffness reduction, etc., and its constitutive responses, due to matrix cracks may be summarized to produce an equivalent change of properly defined "damage field" in macroscale.

Therefore, the damage characterization of mechanical behavior may be obtained by analyzing deformation process in macroscale through "internal state variable approach or their statistical average" without considering the individual defect. Consider a reference configuration of a damaged laminate body B at time t represented as $X_t(\underline{\sigma}, \underline{\varepsilon}, \mathcal{D})$, where \mathcal{D} is a generalized representation of damage variable due to matrix cracks. The deformation process to be examined is a state change from X_t to $X_{t+dt}(\underline{\sigma} + d\underline{\sigma}, \underline{\varepsilon} + d\underline{\varepsilon}, \mathcal{D} + d\mathcal{D})$. When a reference middle-state $X_t^i(\underline{\sigma} + d\underline{\sigma}, \underline{\varepsilon} + d\underline{\varepsilon}, \mathcal{D})$ defined by confining the invariant damage variable \mathcal{D} during the process from X_t to X_t^i is assumed to exist, then we may obtain the increment of strain as

$$d\underline{\varepsilon} = d\underline{\hat{\varepsilon}} + d\underline{\varepsilon}^d \quad (1a)$$

and stress-strain relation

$$d\underline{\sigma} = \mathbf{E}(\mathcal{D}):d\underline{\varepsilon} - \mathbf{E}(\mathcal{D}):d\underline{\varepsilon}^d \quad (1b)$$

where $\mathbf{E}(\mathcal{D})$ is the equivalent stiffness due to damage \mathcal{D} . Since most epoxy laminates may be characterized as brittle in nature, $d\underline{\varepsilon}$ may thus be taken as an increment of current elastic strain tensor; while $d\underline{\hat{\varepsilon}}$ and $d\underline{\varepsilon}^d$ are defined as the increment of partial elastic strain tensor at a constant damage state \mathcal{D} and the increment of damage strain tensor respectively. It should be emphasized that the damage strain $d\underline{\varepsilon}^d$ is determined not only by \mathcal{D} , but also by the current stress and strain state. In particular, when the damage is invariant or history independent during, say a typical unloading process ($d\mathcal{D} = 0$) $d\underline{\varepsilon}^d$ also vanishes.

The damage strain defined above can clarify the difference between damage and damage effects on materials. In the conventional approaches, damage variable is generally formulated without distinguishing these two important but distinct physical phenomena. In fact, from the point of damage micro-mechanism, the initiation and development of damage are related to the re-arrangements of material micro-structures, which may cause an instantaneous re-distribution of internal strain fields. Therefore, the final experimental observation of material degradation actually results from such a change strain state. This phenomena may be considered analogous to the classical theory of "Griffith brittle fracture". To be able to properly differentiate these two physical aspects of "damage" is important in the formulation of material constitutive relation, because damage effects variable, i.e. $\underline{\varepsilon}^d$ is usually not an internal state variable, i.e. damage variable.

For the sake of simplicity, let us consider \mathcal{D} expressed in terms of a two parameter representation model as

$$\mathcal{D} = (\mathbf{D}, \omega) \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{D} is a second rank damage tensor similar to conventional models with vanishing initial state and ω denotes a scalar damage variable. In general, consider a representative volume V in a damaged lamina, which contains k number of damages such as cracks or crack-like entities. The relating damage variable was defined through a statistical average of the volume as to[3]

$$\mathbf{D} = \frac{1}{V} \int_{S(k)} \mathbf{D}^k(D^k, g^k, \alpha^k(n), \dots, \mathbf{V}^k, \mathbf{b}^k, \mathbf{V}^k \mathbf{b}^k, \mathbf{V}^k \mathbf{V}^k, \mathbf{b}^k \mathbf{b}^k, \dots) \cdot dS(k) \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{b}^k is defined as the residual micro-displacement vector at a point on $s(k)$ between two relative sides of a crack when the damaged material is completely unloaded; \mathbf{V}^k represents the components of matrix crack area vector of $s(k)$; D^k and g^k are the density of matrix cracks and the coefficient of crack geometry respectively, while $\alpha^k(n)$ are the

parameters due to secondary material defect events, such as the interaction between cracks, stress concentrations, etc. Let axis e_1 be the fiber direction of lamina. Since matrix cracking must always grow parallel to fiber direction, the effects of components of V_1 and b_1 on damage may be neglected. Then, with the condition vanishing damage \mathbf{D} when crack vector $\mathbf{V} = 0$ (no crack or crack-like damage entities exist), \mathbf{D} finally take the form

$$D_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & D_{22} & D_{23} \\ 0 & D_{32} & D_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where the component D_{22} represents matrix cracking, D_{33} , D_{23} characterize laminate delamination and the interaction between matrix cracking and delamination, respectively.

2.2. Constitutive relation based on thermodynamics

From thermodynamics, the damage process, as an irreversible process, satisfies the principles of irreversible thermodynamics known as the conservation of energy law (first law) and the production of entropy law (second law). Confine our attention to the purely mechanical deformation processes with quasi-static damage growth, for which the total heat supply changes per unit time, $\dot{Q} = 0$, the first law of thermodynamics requires that (referred to the unit mass)

$$\dot{U} = \dot{W} = \dot{W}^e + \dot{W}^d = \frac{1}{\rho} \underline{\sigma} : \dot{\underline{\varepsilon}} \quad (5)$$

where $\dot{W} = \frac{1}{\rho} \underline{\sigma} : \dot{\underline{\varepsilon}}$ represents the total strain energy rate of applied load, \dot{W}^e and \dot{W}^d denote the incremental rate of material elastic strain energy and the dissipative power due to damage nucleation and propagation. The incremental rate of elastic energy \dot{W}^e

$$\dot{W}^e = \frac{1}{2\rho} (\underline{\dot{\sigma}} : \underline{\varepsilon} + \underline{\sigma} : \dot{\underline{\varepsilon}}) = \frac{1}{\rho} \underline{\varepsilon} : \mathbf{E}(D) : \dot{\underline{\varepsilon}} - \frac{1}{2\rho} \dot{\underline{\varepsilon}} : \mathbf{E}(D) : \dot{\underline{\varepsilon}} \quad (6)$$

where $\dot{\underline{\sigma}}$ is given by eq.(1). Then, the second law of thermodynamics states that there exists a state function $S(a_k, T)$, known as entropy which requires the following inequality

$$T \cdot \dot{S} \geq \dot{Q} = 0 \quad (7)$$

From eq.(5,-,7), the constitutive equations can be conveniently derived by employing the free energy function defined by $\phi = U - T \cdot S$. Conventionally, the form of ϕ is often formulated in conjunction with the material elastic strain energy W^e , and usually represented as $\phi = W^e + \phi_2(\omega)$. Then, with eq.(6), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\phi}(\underline{\varepsilon}, \underline{\varepsilon}^d, \omega, t) &= \dot{W}^e + (\dot{\phi}_2(\omega)) = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \underline{\varepsilon}} : \dot{\underline{\varepsilon}} + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \underline{\varepsilon}^d} : \dot{\underline{\varepsilon}}^d + (\dot{\phi}_2(\omega)) \\ &= \frac{1}{\rho} \underline{\sigma} : \dot{\underline{\varepsilon}} - \frac{1}{\rho} \underline{\sigma}^d : \dot{\underline{\varepsilon}}^d + (\dot{\phi}_2(\omega)) = \frac{1}{\rho} \underline{\varepsilon} : \mathbf{E} : \dot{\underline{\varepsilon}} - \frac{1}{2\rho} \dot{\underline{\varepsilon}} : \mathbf{E} : \dot{\underline{\varepsilon}}^d + \dot{\phi}_2(\omega) \cdot \dot{\omega} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where

$$\underline{\sigma} = \rho \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \underline{\varepsilon}} = \mathbf{E} : \underline{\varepsilon}; \quad \underline{\sigma}^d = -\rho \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \underline{\varepsilon}^d} = -\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{E} : \underline{\varepsilon}; \quad B = \dot{\phi}_2(\omega) \quad (9)$$

By combining eqs.(6,8) and eq.(9), the second law of thermodynamics of eq.(7) takes the form as

$$\rho \cdot T \cdot \dot{S} = \Psi(\underline{\varepsilon}^d, \dot{\omega}) = \underline{\sigma}^d : \dot{\underline{\varepsilon}}^d - B \cdot \dot{\omega} = L \geq 0 \quad (10)$$

This is also known as the Clausius-Duhem inequality; $\Psi(\underline{\varepsilon}^d, \dot{\omega})$ is called as the dissipation function and $\underline{\sigma}^d$ and B are the associated variables of $\underline{\varepsilon}^d$.

Let the dissipation function in the space be $\mathbf{a} = (\underline{\varepsilon}^d, \dot{\omega})$ represented by dissipation surfaces $\Psi = \Psi_0 = \text{constant}$. In light of the principle of maximal dissipation rate[4], the constitutive relation of materials may be derived in terms of the orthogonality condition. However, since the existence of damage is attributed to the material micro-structure rearrangements, the dissipation rate should even be expressed by the generalized state variables in terms of the hypothesis of "equivalence of damage dissipation rate", as

The deforming processes of damaged material can be alternatively described by the generalized strain and damage strain ($\underline{\tilde{\epsilon}}$ and $\underline{\tilde{\epsilon}}^d$) and generalized $\underline{\tilde{\omega}}$. while, the state of $\underline{\sigma}$, $\underline{\sigma}^d$ and \mathbf{B} are accordingly expressed by the generalized stresses and damage stress ($\underline{\tilde{\sigma}}$ and $\underline{\tilde{\sigma}}^d$) and generalized $\underline{\tilde{B}}$. In addition, the related total dissipation rate is equal to the one given by eq.(10) as

$$L = \underline{\tilde{\sigma}}^d : \underline{\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}}^d - \mathbf{B} \cdot \dot{\omega} = \underline{\tilde{\sigma}}^d : \underline{\tilde{\epsilon}}^{\cdot d} - \underline{\tilde{B}} \cdot \underline{\tilde{\omega}}^{\cdot} \quad (11)$$

Therefore, the corresponding generalized orthogonality condition may be easily deduced:

There exists a potential function $\tilde{F}_d(\underline{\tilde{\sigma}}^d, \underline{\tilde{B}})$ or alternatively, $\tilde{F}_d(\underline{\tilde{\sigma}}^d, \mathbf{R}, \underline{\tilde{B}})$, for which the generalized dissipative force $\underline{\tilde{\sigma}}^d$, and $\underline{\tilde{B}}$ corresponding to a generalized damaged strain $\underline{\tilde{\epsilon}}^d$ and $\underline{\tilde{\omega}}^{\cdot}$ are orthogonal at the surface of $\tilde{F}_d(\underline{\tilde{\sigma}}^d, \underline{\tilde{B}}) = 0$. It gives

$$d\underline{\tilde{\epsilon}}^d = d\lambda \cdot \frac{\partial \tilde{F}_d}{\partial \underline{\tilde{\sigma}}^d}; \quad d\underline{\tilde{\omega}} = d\lambda \cdot \frac{\partial \tilde{F}_d}{\partial (-\underline{\tilde{B}})} = d\lambda \cdot \tilde{F}_2(\underline{\tilde{B}}); \quad d\mathbf{D} = d\lambda \cdot \frac{\partial \tilde{F}_d}{\partial \mathbf{R}} \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{R} is the thermodynamic conjugated force of damage tensor \mathbf{D} and $d\lambda$ is a non-negative parameter determined by the damage flow condition $d\tilde{F}_d(\underline{\tilde{\sigma}}^d, \underline{\tilde{B}}) = 0$. For ease of illustration in what followed, we omit the cap “ \sim ” unless otherwise stated. Without loss of generality, consider the following form of F_d

$$F_d(\mathbf{R}, \underline{\sigma}^d) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \underline{\sigma}^{T,d} : \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{R}) : \underline{\sigma}^d - \tilde{F}_2(\underline{\tilde{B}}) \quad (13)$$

Choose $F_2(\mathbf{B}) = 0.5 \cdot \mathbf{B}^2$ and take a power approach law of ω for \mathbf{B} as

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B}_0 + g(\omega) = \mathbf{B}_0 + k \cdot \omega^\nu \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{B}_0 is the initial damage hardening threshold and k and ν are constants.

Provided that the evaluation of damage \mathbf{D} is determined only by its associated force \mathbf{R} . The relation between \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{R} is considered in terms of a linear approximation for damage \mathbf{D} , as

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{K} : \mathbf{D} \quad \text{or} \quad d\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{K} : d\mathbf{D} = d\lambda \cdot \mathbf{K} : \frac{\partial \tilde{F}_d}{\partial \mathbf{R}} \quad (15)$$

where tensor \mathbf{K} is a laminate constant tensor which may be determined by experiments. In particular, for virgin transverse isotropic material, \mathbf{K} reduces to a symmetric tensor with two non-zero components, as given below (using Voigt notation K_{ij} , $i, j = 1, -, 6$)

$$K_{22} = K_{33} = c_\lambda \quad (16)$$

with a vanishing D_{11} (or R_{11}) as indicated by eq.(4) and the non-coupling effects between the components of damage variable \mathbf{D} .

2.3. The representation of incremental equivalent stiffness

Denote the material equivalent stiffness at times t and $t+dt$ as $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{D})$ and $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{D}+d\mathbf{D})$ respectively. The equivalent stiffness may be derived in light of a linear stress-strain relation in the unloading process or re-loading process after unloading by ignoring higher order infinitesimal terms for approximation of $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{D}+d\mathbf{D})$, as

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{D}+d\mathbf{D}) - \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{D}) = - \frac{1}{2} d\lambda \cdot \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{D}) : \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{K} : \mathbf{D}) : \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{D}) \quad (17)$$

Similarly, the equivalent compliance is

$$\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{R}+d\mathbf{R}) - \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{R}) = \frac{1}{2} d\lambda \cdot \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{R}) \quad (18)$$

In view of the classical invariant theory, the scalar function, \hat{F}_d , determined jointly by \mathbf{R} and $\underline{\sigma}^d$ may be explicitly formulated by the irreducible integrity bases of $\underline{\sigma}^d$ and \mathbf{R} . Take the Cartesian decomposition of $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}^s + \mathbf{R}^a$ (or $\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{D}^s + \mathbf{D}^a$). The relevant irreducible integrity bases for virgin transverse isotropic materials are given by Smith[5] as

$$\begin{aligned}
I_1 &= \sigma_{11}^d ; \quad I_2 = \sigma_{22}^d + \sigma_{33}^d ; \quad I_3 = (\sigma_{22}^d - \sigma_{33}^d)^2 + 4 \cdot (\sigma_{32}^d)^2 \\
I_4 &= (\sigma_{21}^d)^2 + (\sigma_{13}^d)^2 ; \quad I_5 = R_{22}^s + R_{33}^s ; \quad I_6 = (\sigma_{22}^d - \sigma_{33}^d)(R_{22}^s - R_{33}^s) + 4 \cdot \sigma_{23}^d \cdot R_{23}^s \\
I_7 &= [(\sigma_{12}^d)^2 - (\sigma_{13}^d)^2](R_{22}^s - R_{33}^s) + 4 \cdot R_{23}^s \cdot (\sigma_{12}^d \cdot \sigma_{13}^d)
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Let us take a linear approximation of \mathbf{R} for \hat{F}_d (neglecting higher order terms) and quadratic approach of $\underline{\sigma}^d$. Using the Voigt notation, we have

$$\hat{F}_d = J_i^{(1)}(R_{kl}^s) \cdot \sigma_i^d + J^{(2)}(R_{kl}^s) + 0.5 \cdot J_{ij}(R_{kl}^s) \cdot \sigma_i^d \cdot \sigma_j^d \tag{20}$$

(k,l=1-3, and i,j =1-6)

With $d\epsilon^d$ vanishing at initial state (or/un-loading) for which $\underline{\sigma}^d=0$, we further have

$$J_k^{(1)}(R_{kl}^s) = 0 ; \quad J^{(2)}(R_{kl}^s) = 0 \tag{21}$$

This verifies that the expression for \hat{F}_d coincides with our previous assumption in eq.(13).

According to eqs.(19,20), we notice that the asymmetric part \mathbf{R}^a will disappear in the final expression due to the constrain of material symmetries (eq.(19)). This implies that the mechanical response of a damaged material characterized by one tensorial damage of rank two may be equivalently characterized by its symmetric part, and the explicit expressions of constitutive relation are unchanged under the linear approach of \mathbf{R} (or damage tensor) for F_d (as in eq.20). Therefore, without loss of generality, confine our attention on damaged materials related to the symmetric tensor \mathbf{R}^s only by excluding its asymmetric part from \mathbf{R} in the following discussion and denote it also simply by \mathbf{R} for ease of illustration.

On the other hand, for cracks or crack-like damage entities it is well accepted that material properties in macroscale along one direction are independent from the components of damage variable which are perpendicular to this direction in terms of *statistical average*, i.e. J_{11} is independent on R_{22} and R_{33} . For illustration purpose, define $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{R})$ in the principle directional coordinate system ($\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3$) of \mathbf{R} . Referring to eqs.(4,15), R_2, R_3 are the only two non-vanished principle values of \mathbf{R} . \mathbf{J} may hence be reduced to $\mathbf{J} = \mathbf{J}^0 + \mathbf{J}^1$, where \mathbf{J}^0 and \mathbf{J}^1 are

$$J_{ij}^0 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \alpha_o & \alpha_o \\ & 1 & \beta_o \\ & & 1 \\ S & & 2(1-\beta_o) \\ & & & \eta_o \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad J_{ij}^1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \alpha(R_2+R_3) & \alpha(R_2+R_3) & & & \\ & (R_2+R_3) & \beta(R_2+R_3) & & & 0 \\ & & (R_2+R_3) & & & \\ & & & 2(1-\beta)(R_2+R_3) & & \\ & S & & \eta(R_2+R_3) & & \\ & & & & \eta(R_2+R_3) & \end{bmatrix} \tag{22}$$

where $\alpha_o, \alpha, \beta_o, \beta$ and η_o, η are laminates constants which may be determined experimentally.

3. IN-PLANE STIFFNESS REDUCTION AND EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

3.1. Formulation of in-plane stiffness reduction due to matrix cracking

In-plane stiffness reduction of laminates has been a subject of intensive study. Consider the particular properties of matrix cracking within individual lamina as mentioned in section(1). Most of conventional studies represented the constitutive responses by simplifying matrix cracks to "geometrically idealized plane cracks" (Hashin[6], Yang[7] and Talreja[8]) which are developed perpendicular to the interface only. In light of this approximation adapted in the conventional models, let us similarly confine our attention to constitutive responses of a damaged laminated specimen dominated by such type of matrix cracks prior to the onset of delamination. \mathbf{R} may hence be reduced to $\mathbf{R} = \text{diag}(0, R_2, 0)$ in its principle co-ordinate system and \mathbf{J} becomes

$$J_{ij} = \frac{1}{E_2} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \alpha_o + \alpha R & 0 \\ S & 1 + R & 0 \\ & & \eta_o + \eta R \end{bmatrix} \tag{23}$$

where the fiber direction of 90-degree ply is oriented at e_1 ; while e_3 is perpendicular to the laminate plane and $R=2.0 \cdot R_2$.

Then from eq.(18), the compliance reduction of a damaged lamina is obtained by

$$\begin{aligned} S_{11}(R+dR) - S_{11}(R) &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot d\lambda \cdot (1 + R) \\ S_{12}(R+dR) - S_{12}(R) &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot d\lambda \cdot (\alpha_0 + \alpha R) \\ S_{66}(R+dR) - S_{66}(R) &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot d\lambda \cdot (\eta_0 + \eta R) \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

where $d\lambda$ may be derived with damage flow condition of $dF(\underline{\sigma}^d, B) = 0$, as

$$d\lambda = \frac{\hat{\partial} F_d}{2 \partial \underline{\sigma}^d} : E(R) : d\underline{\epsilon} \left/ \left(B^2 - 0.5 \cdot \underline{\sigma}^d : \frac{\partial J}{\partial R} : \underline{\sigma}^d + \frac{\hat{\partial} F_d}{2 \partial \underline{\sigma}^d} : E(R) : J : \underline{\sigma}^d \right) \right. \quad (25)$$

for progressing damage processes.

3.2. Experiments and results

Stiffness loss of Carbon/epoxy (T300/934) laminated specimens of various stacking sequences is measured. The geometry of the specimens is selected as $250 \times 25 \times (2.0-2.6)$ mm according to the ASTM standard. The virgin material elastic constants used in this analysis were measured by uni-directional lamina:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{11} &= 121.2 \text{GPa}; \quad E_{22} = E_{33} = 8.08 \text{GPa}; \quad \nu_{12} = \nu_{23} = \nu_{31} = 0.32; \\ G_{12} &= G_{23} = G_{31} = 6.81 \text{GPa} \end{aligned}$$

The laminates with stacking sequences of $[0_n, 90_m]_s$ (six specimens), $n=1,2,3$, $[\pm 45]_s$ (four specimens) and $[0, 90, \pm 45]_s$ (four specimens) were tested.

Since the stiffness of $[0_2, 90_6]_s$ are expected to exhibit the largest decrease in magnitude after matrix cracking among the above specimens, the measured variation of stiffness is selected in this analysis to deduce the change in laminate constants. The percentage reductions of Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio are measured as shown in Fig.1 and the associated laminates constants are then calculated from eq.(25) using the Least Square Method:

$$\alpha_0 = -0.1826; \quad \alpha = -0.002524; \quad B_0 = 81.59; \quad k = 2.861; \quad \nu = 0.5323; \quad c_\lambda = 0.0033$$

With the above parameters determined, the predicted stiffness losses of cross-ply laminates $[0_3, 90_3]_s$ and $[0_2, 90_4]_s$ based on the proposed model are compared with experimental results, as shown in Fig.2 & 3. Good correlations are indicated. It may be found that a sharp stiffness decrease occurred soon after the onset of matrix cracking as the point A in Fig.1. According to the physical mechanism of propagation of cracks in brittle materials, the above phenomena is in fact related to ultimate unstable failure of 90-degree plies due to matrix cracking. At this stage, a number of matrix cracks run across the width of the specimen. The corresponding nominal simple tensile stress-strain (perpendicular to fiber direction) in 90-degree ply is illustrated in Fig.4. A maximum of 13% loss of Young's modulus, while 46% loss of Poisson's ratio were observed. In addition, after the laminate strain is over 0.8%-0.9%, the variation of stiffness tends to be stable, say less than 4-percent from 0.8% to ultimate failure.

On the other hand, the laminate parameters η_0 and η are related to the reduction of shear modulus as indicated by eq.(25). Fig.5 provides the measured loss of shear modulus. Constants η_0 and η are calculated as

$$\eta_0 = 0.4077; \quad \eta = 0.002169;$$

The stiffness loss of multi-directional laminates is finally analyzed by employing staking sequence of $[0, 90, \pm 45]_s$. As indicated in Fig.6, the predicted ones are lower than the measured results. The main reason is that matrix cracks are assumed to behave like "idealized plane cracks" as discussed in the above section. However, due to the presence of out-of-plane stresses singularity resulted by the mismatches of laminae elastic properties

and the discontinuities of geometries of laminates, a number of secondary cracks (curved) and oblique cracks may have occurred near the free edges, especially in multi-directional laminates, which may hence influence the variation of laminates stiffness. Allen et al[10] have discussed the effects of the existences of curved cracks and oblique cracks on the stiffness loss of cross-ply laminates by characterizing damage in terms of the concept of DM. According to their analyzed results both experimentally and theoretically, the effect of oblique cracks on the out-of-plane stiffness is considerable, while on the axial stiffness is comparatively small if curved cracks are simplified to plane matrix cracks perpendicular to the laminate interface. The same conclusion may also be realized for cross-ply laminates in the present investigation, see Fig.1. However, as indicated in Fig.6, the effect of stress singularity on the in-plane stiffness of multi-directional laminates is considerable. The solid line in Fig.6 presents the results obtained with finite element analysis by employing the material constants determined above. Future study on this problem should involve a detailed analysis on the determination of material constants jointly with the existence of oblique cracks.

4. CONCLUSION

Damage characterization of stiffness loss for laminates is systematically discussed, especially on the change of shear modulus, indicating that such a stiffness loss of various stacking sequence due to matrix cracking can be described by two damage variables, i.e. D and ω , based on the theory of DM. A good agreement between the theoretical and experimental results for cross-ply, except of $[0,90,\pm 45]_s$, has been observed. However, it can be rationally expected that with proper consideration on the effects of secondary cracks in the determination of laminates constants, such as η_0 and η_90 in terms of finite element analysis, the predicted results should be improved.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of this investigation by Harbin Institute of Technology, China, and also express their appreciation to Mr. Wang Changli and many other staff in the Institute Central Laboratory of the Institute for their assistance and valuable advice during the experimental phase of the investigation and the fabrication of the specimens.

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Fig. 1 Stiffness Variation of $[0_2, 90_3]$ Carbon/epoxy Laminates Under Static Tensile Test

Fig. 2 Stiffness Variation of $[0_1, 90_1]$ Carbon/epoxy Laminates Under tensile Test

Fig. 3 Stiffness Variation of $[0_3, 90_3]$ Carbon/Epoxy Laminates Under Static Tensile Test

Fig. 4 Normal Stress and Strain Relation In 90 Ply

Fig. 5 Variation of Shear Modulus of Carbon/Epoxy Laminates Measured By $[+45_3]$

Fig. 6 The Loss of Young's Modulus of Carbon/Epoxy Laminates $[0,90,\pm 45]_s$ Under Static Tensile Test